

STYL-EN ROUTE APPROACH TO THE STYLOID PROCESS

RESECTION

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Abstract

Objectives:

We report a case series of four cases involving an elongated styloid process presenting with persistent cervicofacial pain, both unilateral and bilateral. In all cases, conservative management failed to alleviate the symptoms. Surgical intervention through styloidectomy was performed by various approaches like trans-oral, extended submandibular and modified retromandibular approach, resulting in significant symptom relief in all approaches, highlighting the effectiveness of modified retromandibular approach is better than trans-oral, extended sub-mandibular approach for styloidectomy in managing such cases.

Study design:

Case series

Conclusion:

Elongated styloid process causing intermittent neuralgia during mouth opening, sharp impingement in the pharynx while turning the neck or during deglutition, and other symptoms commonly associated with Eagle's syndrome is increasingly recognized as a clinical entity. In our series of four patients with an elongated styloid process, all underwent unilateral or bilateral styloidectomy after failure of medical management, resulting in complete relief of symptoms. Surgical approaches included a transoral/peroral approach in one patient, a bilateral extended submandibular approach in another, and a modified retromandibular approach in two patients. The modified retromandibular approach provided excellent access to the styloid apparatus and was associated with fewer postoperative complications. Based on our experience, we advocate the modified retromandibular approach for styloidectomy, following thorough clinical and radiological evaluation in patients unresponsive to conservative therapy. Additionally, careful assessment of the patient's psychological status may help validate the authenticity of symptoms in cases with unresolved complaints.

Keywords

Elongated styloid process, Eagle's syndrome, Sub mandibular approach, Modified Retromandibular approach, Tran oral Approach, Facial nerve injury

INTRODUCTION:

The hallmark of Eagle's syndrome, which was first identified by otolaryngologist Eagles in 1937, is pain in the neck and throat that travels to the mastoid area. This disorder is brought on by calcification of the stylohyoid ligament or extension of the styloid process over 25 mm [1,2]. Headache, dysphagia, odynophagia, mastoid discomfort, ear pain, and dysphonia are among the clinical signs of Eagle's syndrome. These symptoms are frequently brought on by excessive neck extension or rapid neck movements. In contrast to the classical examination for the extended styloid process, which includes probing the styloid process in the tonsillar space, the clinical examination usually reveals the obstruction of the tonsillar fossa [3]. A comprehensive history and physical examination, which includes transpharyngeal palpation of the styloid process with the patient's mouth open, can help distinguish Eagle's syndrome from other facial neuralgias and temporomandibular joint diseases. Furthermore, the diagnosis may be supported by radiographic methods such Towne's views, lateral cephalograms, panoramic radiographs, open-mouth odontoid views, lateral oblique views, and posteroanterior skull views [4]. Both conservative and surgical methods can be used to treat Eagle's syndrome. Heat fermentation, transpharyngeal injections of lignocaine, and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications are examples of conservative therapy. Transoral or transcervical techniques for styloidectomy may be used in surgical management [5]. Four cases of classical Eagle's syndrome that underwent surgery utilizing three distinct techniques—transoral (TO), extended submandibular (ESM), and modified retromandibular (MRM)—are compared in this report.

Materials & Methods:

Patients undergoing styloid process resection were enrolled in this study from January 2022 to January 2025 with IHEC-Reference Number:IHEC/SDC/OMFS-2306/25/143 Preoperative

evaluation included measurement of the styloid process using cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) and orthopantomogram (OPG). The surgical approach was documented as transoral (TO), extended submandibular (ESM), or modified retromandibular (MRM). Intraoperative difficulty was assessed and recorded by the surgeons. Postoperative outcomes, including wound infection, trismus, and facial nerve injury, were documented and graded according to the House-Brackmann scale. Only patients aged 18 years and older were included, with equal representation of both genders.

Approaches:

Trans Oral Approach [TO]:

The primary complaint of a 28-year-old male patient who arrived to the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery was sporadic pain in the area of his right posterior teeth that got worse when he swallowed and was linked to odynophagia. No dental cavities, pericoronitis, or impacted teeth were found during the intraoral examination, and the temporomandibular joint seemed to be in normal condition. However, pain upon palpation showed bilaterally enlarged styloid processes, and probing of the tonsillar fossa revealed an excessively long styloid process extending from the tonsil fossa. Cone beam computed tomography (Figure 1) was used to confirm the diagnosis of a bilaterally elongated styloid process. This imaging revealed a "S"-shaped bend in the bilateral elongation of the styloid process with a forward course towards the pharynx, resulting in an intraorally palpable impingement in the pharynx. Operative procedure: In the operating room, the patient received general anesthesia and had an intraoral styloidectomy. A transoral incision was made along the ramus's ascending edge and a curved hemostat was used to conduct blunt dissection. The superior constrictor of the pharynx muscle was lateral to the dissection, medial to the medial pterygoid muscle, and posteriorly. After that, the styloid apparatus was revealed, caught

between two hemostats, broken, and removed with ease. 3.0 polyglactin was used for the closure, and for three days, postoperative painkillers and antibiotics were given. On the third postoperative day, the patient was released, and at the one-year follow-up, there were no complaints from either side. (Figure 1)

Extended Submandibular Approach [ESM]:

A 35-year-old woman's primary complaints when she arrived to the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery were dull pain in the throat area and trouble swallowing. The right mastoid and right pharyngeal regions were affected by the occasional, subtle pain. Bending the neck to the ipsilateral side helped to ease it. There were reports of related headaches, dysphagia, discomfort when the tongue was extended, and neck pain that got worse after swallowing. The temporomandibular joint examination revealed no abnormalities, and the patient's prior medical history was noncontributory. Upon extraoral physical examination, a tiny, bony, firm, and tender projection was found at the anterior border of the sternocleidomastoid muscle in the right submandibular region. There was no evidence of infection or deterioration, and all third molars were impacted. When the tonsillar fossa was palpated, the styloid process bone was felt. Radiographic analysis Cone beam computed tomography, which displays an extended styloid process with S curvature moving downward and forward, further confirms the bilateral elongated styloid process seen in the orthopantomogram. Operative procedure: Following extensive examinations, the patient was scheduled for surgery under general anesthesia to do a styleloidectomy on the right side exclusively using an extraoral route, addressing the primary complaint on that side. For the extended submandibular (ESM) approach, an extraoral incision was made along the ramus's ascending border, passing through the epidermis and skin before reaching the dermis. The posterior part of the masseter muscle is then dissected using blunt dissection in

the subplatysmal plane using a curved hemostat. After exposing the styloid apparatus, the styloid process is degloved by making an incision along the periosteum (without affecting the attachments). Hemostatic forceps were used to hold the bare styloid, which was then broken, released, and taken out. 3.0 polyglactin was subsequently used to close the muscles and mucosa, and 4.0 polypropylene was used to close the skin. Follow-up and postoperative treatment were routine. After receiving surgical antibiotics (Amoxicillin 500 mg \times 3 days) and analgesics (Aceclofenac 325 mg + paracetamol 100 mg BD for three days), the patients were released with the proper postoperative instructions 24 hours later. On the seventh postoperative day, the extraoral sutures were taken out, and routine checkups were conducted.(Figure 2)

Modified Retromandibular Approach [MRM]:

Operative procedure: Following extensive examinations, the patient was scheduled for surgery under general anesthesia to do a styloidectomy on the right side exclusively using an extraoral route, addressing the primary complaint on that side. For the extended retromandibular approach, an extraoral incision was made along the 2cm away from ramus's ascending border, passing through the epidermis and skin before reaching the dermis. The anterior part of the sternocleidomastoid muscle is then skeletonized, dissected using blunt dissection in the after subplatysmal plane using a curved hemostat. After exposing the styloid apparatus, the styloid process is degloved by making an incision along the periosteum (without affecting the attachments). Alley's forceps were used to hold the bare styloid, which was then broken, released, and taken out. 3.0 polyglactin was subsequently used to close the muscles and mucosa, and 4.0 polypropylene was used to close the skin.(Figure 3)

Results:

One patient with transient facial nerve paralysis underwent surgery using the ESM approach with grade III–IV moderate dysfunction with incomplete eye closure, and all four patients who were diagnosed with elongated styloid process underwent styloidectomy using TO, ESM, and MRM approaches [TABLE 1]

Table1: House Brackman grading system of Facial Nerve

GRADE	DISCRIPTION	CHARACTERISTICS
I	Normal	Normal facial function
II	Mild dysfunction	Slight weakness on close inspection; normal tone and symmetry at rest
III	Moderate dysfunction	Obvious weakness +/- asymmetry, but not disfiguring; synkinesis, contracture or hemifacial spasm; complete eye closure with effort
IV	Moderately severe dysfunction	Obvious weakness or disfiguring asymmetry; normal symmetry and tone at rest; incomplete eye closure
V	Severe dysfunction	Barely perceptible motion; asymmetry at rest
VI	Total paralysis	No movement

The elongated styloid process measured averagely from 25mm to the largest 40mm in size. Additionally, all patients had graded facial nerve function post operatively based on the house Brackman grading system [21] during the first week and sixth month post operatively. Another

patient experienced modest marginal mandibular dysfunction (Grade II), which led to a small weakening in the lower lip. [TABLE 2]

Table 2 : Comparison of Approaches Used for Individual Patients underwent styloidectomy

S. NO	AGE OF PATIENT	GENDER	PRE-OP MEASUREMENT OF ELONGATED STYLOID	LATERALITY	APPROACH USED
1	23	M	25mm	Unilateral	Transoral approach
2	25	F	28mm and 40mm	Bilateral	Extended submandibular
3	35	F	40mm	Unilateral	Extended submandibular
4	49	M	30mm	Unilateral	Modified retromandibular

After undergoing a TO approach, which lasted an average of 90 minutes under general anesthesia, the patient developed post-operative dysphagia and trismus as a result of excessive soft tissue retraction. The MRM procedure took an average of 120 minutes from skin incision to closure and the patient had a small scar with no signs of infection or damage to the facial nerve. After undergoing ESM and MRM procedures, none of the three patients needed a drain.[TABLE 3]

Table 3: Assessment of Facial Nerve Functioning & Difficulty Encountered in Various Approaches

SNO	TYPE OF APPROACH	DURATION OF PROCEDURE	DIFFICULTY ENCOUNTERED	POST-OPERATIVE COMPLICATION	FACIAL NERVE GRADING AT ONE WEEK	FACIAL NERVE GRADING AT 6 MONTHS
1	Transoral	90 minutes	Access, Retraction Difficulty	Dysphagia, Trismus	Nil	Nil
2	Extended submandibular - Bilateral	120 minutes	Intra operative twitching of facial nerve, meticulous surgical procedure, extensive scar	Left side incomplete eye closure for 6 months	III	I
3	Extended submandibular - Unilateral	120 minutes	Intra operative twitching of facial nerve, meticulous surgical procedure, extensive scar	Mild marginal mandibular nerve palsy	II	I

4	Modified retromandibular	120 minutes	Retractions Depth Less Visual for assistants	Nil	I	I
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Discussion:

The styloid process is a bony protuberance situated between the internal and external carotid arteries, extending 2.5 cm from the inferior portion of the petrous temporal bone. The styloid process is connected to a number of muscles and ligaments, such as the stylohyoid, stylopharyngeus, styloglossus, stylohyoid ligament, and stylomandibular ligament. Eagle's syndrome, sometimes referred to as "Stylohyoid syndrome," is typified by an aberrant angle, ossification of the styloid, or extension of the styloid process (>25 mm) [6,7]. Intraoral and extraoral surgical methods are utilized to shorten the styloid process. Although each technique has pros and cons, both were used in this case study. Despite having less access, the intraoral method required less time during surgery—roughly 90 minutes. There was no incision or scar because of the short recovery time and the intraoral incision's ability to heal itself. Although the extraoral method provided great access, it left a noticeable scar. The length of the procedure was extended to around two hours, and mouth opening was restricted for two weeks after the procedure before gradually increasing in the third week. After a month, the mouth openness returned to normal [7,8]. Research comparing the two methods' postoperative efficacy has not discovered any appreciable differences. In comparison to the trans-cervical technique, the intraoral approach was judged to be safer because it resulted in less surgical trauma, less surgical time, and no scar. However, when vessels were injured because of inadequate vision, the intraoral technique was found to be

unsuccessful at stopping bleeding. Additionally, although trying to leave the smallest residue of the styloid process, the intraoral technique has limited visibility of the surgical field, the potential for deep cervical infection, and the danger of neurovascular injury. Critics point to the extra-oral approach's lengthy duration, high morbidity rate, and potential involvement of nearby anatomical systems [7-9]. The extraoral method, on the other hand, offers more exposure to the surgical site without hindrance from the depth of the field or the mouth opening. This method lessens the risk of a deep cervical infection while improving visibility in bleeding instances. Nevertheless, it requires more time to operate and may cause internal carotid thrombosis, subcutaneous cervical emphysema, damage to the facial nerve's marginal mandibular branch, and a scar on the neck [10-11]. The differential diagnosis for Eagle's syndrome includes facial pain, glossopharyngeal and trigeminal neuralgia, myofascial pain dysfunction syndrome, temporal arteritis, migraine or cluster headache, pain related to impacted third molars or pericoronitis, and temporomandibular joint disorder (TMD) [12-14]. An extraoral approach may be employed if the styloid process in the tonsillar fossa cannot be palpated. To prevent significant surgery in the parapharyngeal space, a lengthy recovery period, and increased operating expenses, open surgery should be selected when the styloid process takes an unusual course, is exceptionally long, or extends towards the lateral cervical region. The co-morbidity of the patient as well as the surgeon's inclination and experience may influence intraoral or extraoral techniques. In this investigation, 3.0 polyglactin was used to close the muscles and mucosa, 4.0 polypropylene was used to close the skin in the extraoral approach, and 3.0 polyglactin was used to close the site in the intraoral approach [15,16]. Silver nanoparticle coatings [17], cyanoacrylate [18], and antibiotic-coated suture materials [19] are examples of recent developments in suture materials that promote improved wound healing. However, polyglactin, an absorbable suture material that promotes improved wound healing, was used predominantly to close both cases due to the defect site [20].

Conclusion:

Comparing the MRM strategy to the ESM and TO approaches, the former has better exposure. The MRM technique additionally clears the subplatysmal plane to protect the infraparotid area and facial nerve branches. With no vascular anatomical structure obstructing this access, this method precisely positions itself anterior to the sternocleidomastoid muscle and provides direct vision of the styloid in transit. According to this study, the ERM technique is the most effective transcervical strategy when compared to intraoral as well.

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